

and increased productive tillers and IR50 grain yield (see table). There was little difference between carriers. Preemergence oxadiazon EC reduced early rice growth

but effectively controlled grasses, sedges, and aquatic weeds such as *Marsilea quadrifolia* and *Monochoria vaginalis*. It gave 4.7-5.9 t grain yield/ha compared with

3.7 t/ha for the unweeded plot. Mixing an EC formulation of preemergence herbicide with carriers, or direct sprinkling, is simple and economical. □

Rice field weeds of Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya

R. C. Cheruiyot, Kenyatta University College, Botany Department, P. O. Box 43844, Nairobi, Kenya

The Mwea Irrigation Scheme is the largest rice growing area in Kenya. It is near Mount Kenya, about 100 km north

Weeds of Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya.^a

Weed species	Lifeform	Habitat
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) DC.	E	XO ●
<i>Ammannia auriculata</i> Willd.	E	XO
<i>A. baccifera</i> L.	E	X ●
<i>A. prieuriana</i> Guill & Perr.	E	XO ●
<i>Aponogeton absynicum</i> Hochst. ex A. Rich	FL	X ●
<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L.	S	X ■ θ●
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	E	XO θ●
<i>C. immensus</i> C. B. Clarke	E	XO θ●
<i>C. latifolius</i> Poir	E	XO θ●
<i>Diplachne caudata</i> K. Schum	E	XO θ●
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	E	XO θ●
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	FF	X ●
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	E	XO ●
<i>L. prostrata</i> Roxb.	E	XO ●
<i>L. stolonifera</i> (Guill. & Perr.) Raven	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Mariscus assimilis</i> (Steud.) Podlech	E	XO θ●
<i>Marsilea macrocarpa</i> Presl.	FL	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Najas graminea</i> Del.	S	XI ■ θ●
<i>Nymphaea caerulea</i> Savign	FL	X θ●
<i>Ricciocarpus natans</i> (L.) Corda	FF	X
<i>Scirpus confusus</i> N. E. Brown	E	XO θ●
<i>Sesbania sesban</i> (L.) Merr	E	XO θ●
<i>Sphaeranthus bullatus</i> Mattf.	E	XO ●
<i>S. cyathuloides</i> O. Hoffm.	E	XO ●
<i>S. suaveolens</i> (Forsk.) DC.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	E	XO ■ θ●
<i>T. latifolia</i> L.	E	XO ■ θ●

^aE = emergent, FL = floating-leaved, S = submersed, FF = free-floating, X = inside rice crop, O = on levees of major canals, ■ = inside major canals, ▲ = inside major canals but floating, θ = inside feeder canal, ● = inside drains.

Frequency (%)

Distribution of weeds at Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya, 1980-81 growing season.

of Nairobi. We identified the rice field weeds and examined their distribution.

Twenty-nine weeds were identified (see table). According to Sculthorpe's life-form categories, 22 were emergent, 3 floating-leaved, 2 submersed, and 2 free-floating. The major habitats of the weeds were within the rice crop, on the levees of major canals, and inside feeder canals and drains.

Weed distribution was studied in 1980-81 and percentage frequency was scored in 1000 1-m² quadrats. The figure shows the distribution has bimodal peaks

in Sep and Mar. The general decline in weed population between Sep and Dec might be attributed to weeding at the initial stages and drainage as the rice crop matures. The increase between Jan and Mar is due to reflooding and the subsequent reemergence of obligately aquatic weeds. Puddling and rototilling reduce weeds in Aug, when fields are prepared for the next season. The weeds could not be totally eradicated in Dec when dry-land conditions were prevalent because of the persistence of some weeds and nonuniform field preparation. □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Reaction of some upland rices to root-knot nematodes in rubber plantation fields

L. Arayarungsarit, B. Chongkid, S. Suwanbutr, and P. Weerapat, Rice Research Institute, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok, Thailand

In 1984, upland rice lines that were

grown and selected for intercropping in a pararubber crop at Kok-Primeng Rubber Experiment Station were seriously damaged by the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne* spp. Infested plants had root galling, yellowed leaves and leaf sheaths, stunting, and low tillering. Based on the number of root galls, some lines had resistance to the nematode (see table). □